

Antiobesity molecules of natural origin: Call for lead finding acceleration

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Escalation in the number of obese patients among the population during the last decades defined “globesity” as a term for the global obesity epidemic (Jaacks et al., 2019; Vasileva, Marchev, & Georgiev, 2018). Excessive body fat accumulation is strongly associated with comorbidities as type 2 diabetes, hypertension, dyslipidemia, and increased risk of cancer development (Vasileva, Savova, Amirova, Dinkova-Kostova, & Georgiev, 2020). Depending on the severity of obesity, three strategies are applied stepwise: lifestyle changes are recommended as initial level of obesity management, followed by addition of drug treatment, and indication for bariatric surgery for the most morbidly obese. Insufficient efficacy of the available antiobesity approaches, serious adverse reactions of the approved drugs, and the hidden risk from surgical interventions provoke the urgent search of novel treatment lines (Vasileva et al., 2018). Moreover, the healthcare expense is envisioned to rise with every year that makes obesity prevention important strategy for health improvement and reduction of upcoming financial and social burden (Stefan et al., 2020).

Plants utilization in food, cosmetic, and pharmaceutical industry makes them as an invaluable source of diverse bioactive compounds that have beneficial health-promoting effects. Numerous plant extract that are suggested to reduce adiposity through various mechanisms merit further evidence-based confirmation of their potential for obesity management (Vasileva et al., 2018). Despite that, natural products possess an immense potential as source of bioactive compounds and micronutrients, searching for potent antiobesity leads of natural origin is like “looking for the needle in a haystack”—we need to accelerate it! Complex mixtures such as plant extracts need to be carefully profiled aiming at bioactive compound or chemical marker identification. Nevertheless, identification of a major active compound

or combination of compounds rarely occurs. In this regard, plant metabolomics is an advantageous holistic approach toward the natural extracts’ chemical characterization. Combination of hyphenated techniques such as high-resolution mass spectrometry (GC- and/or LC-HRMS/MS) and nuclear magnetic resonance (1D and 2D-NMR) based metabolite fingerprinting provides precise information about both qualitative and quantitative chemical composition of a crude plant extracts. The LC-HRMS/MS molecular network approaches described recently by Wolfender, Queiroz, and Allard (2020) provide novel tools that facilitate identification of plant metabolites.

In this context, our laboratory has developed model system(s) for anti-adipogenic screening in which we have tested a number of potential plant extracts. The assessment of anti-adipogenic potential through intracellular lipid staining is the most common screening method, which is usually followed by the time-consuming bioactivity-guided isolation of natural products aiming at identification of the molecules, responsible for the beneficial effect. This laborious and impeded process, that is often ended without successful lead hit, could be accelerated by integration of the biochemometrics approach (Wolfender, Litaudon, Touboul, & Queiroz, 2019). Once the identification of a suspected active molecule is carried out via biochemometrics, its isolation and bioactivity examination should be confirmed. Next crucial step is the development of methods for sustainable supply of anti-obesity principles (i.e., biotechnological approach and liquid-liquid downstream processing).

The biochemometrics tools (at multi-omics level) shorten the process of leads discovery, which could be eventually implemented in obesity research. Utilization of open databases for metabolite fingerprinting of plant extracts in correlation with their respective

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biological activity (both in vitro and in vivo) would certainly facilitate the process of development of safe and effective natural products for obesity management.

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